

extracted with hexane to remove fat and chlorophyll. The thick viscous mass left after the extraction with hexane was extracted with acetone. The acetone extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to a lib-lib mass. The concentrated acetone extract was dissolved in cold water and kept in a refrigerator for a week whereupon a deposit was obtained which was separated by filtration. The solid mass so obtained was dissolved in a small quantity of ethanol and was adsorbed onto a column of magnesol¹⁰. On eluting with ethyl acetate two flavonoid compounds A and B were obtained which were crystallised from acetone: methanol mixture (1 : 1) and methanol respectively.

The compound A, C₁₅H₁₀O₇ (M⁺ 332), m.p. 316° and compound B, C₁₆H₁₂O₇ (M⁺ 316), m.p. 294° were characterised to be quercetin and rhamnetin respectively by m.m.p. and superimposable IR spectra with the authentic samples.

The aqueous extract left after the removal of the deposit was concentrated to a thick viscous mass. It was extracted with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate extract was concentrated and adsorbed onto a column of magnesol¹⁰. On eluting with ethyl acetate three flavonoid compounds C, C₂₁H₂₀O₁₁, m. p. 186°, D, C₂₀H₁₈O₁₁, m. p. 217° and E, C₂₇H₃₀O₁₆, m. p. 210° were obtained, which were found to be glycosidic in nature. On acid hydrolysis compounds C, D and E gave the same aglycone, m. p. 316° which was identified to be quercetin by m. m. p. with the authentic sample. The hydrolysates from compounds C and D on chromatographic examination revealed the presence of rhamnose and arabinose respectively as sugar moieties while the hydrolysate from compound E showed the presence D-glucose and L-rhamnose. The compounds C, D and E were, therefore, identified as quercitrin, avicularin and rutin, respectively.

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Benzylthiuronium-O-alkyl Dithiocarbonates Potential Pesticides

AZIZ BHAI and K. S. BOPARAI

School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University,
Ujjain-456 010, India

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S-Benzylthiuronium-O-Alkyl Dithio Carbonates have been prepared by the reaction of carbondisulphide with potassium alkoxides followed by treatment with S-benzylthiuronium chloride. Both the cation and anion are likely to exhibit pesticidal characteristics, as such, these salts are expected to be useful pesticides.

Thiuronium salts^{1,2} possess pesticidal properties. Trithiocarbonates³, dithiocarbonates^{4,6}, S-dimethylthiocarbamoyl dithiocarbonates⁷, thiocarbonates⁸ and carbonates⁹ have been used as pesticides. Thiuronium salts of O-alkyl dithiocarbonic acids in which both the ions have biocidal characteristics, are expected to be valuable pesticides. The preparation of benzylthiuronium-O-alkyl dithiocarbonates was, therefore, undertaken. The salts can be prepared in good yields with great ease. The details of the preparation are as follows. Their decomposition points and analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE I—BENZYLTHIURONIUM-O-ALKYL DITHIOCARBONATES DERIVED FROM VARIOUS ALCOHOLS.

Alcohol	*d.p. of salt °C	% Sulphur		% Nitrogen	
		Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
Methyl	75	35.14	35.64	10.26	10.02
Ethyl	80	33.44	33.38	9.76	9.81
n-Propyl	87	31.87	31.87	9.30	9.25
iso-Propyl	104	31.87	32.47	9.30	9.00
n-Butyl	95	30.46	30.37	8.89	8.89
iso-Butyl	83	30.46	30.86	8.89	8.25
iso-Amyl	95	29.16	29.06	8.51	8.11
Benzyl	84	27.49	27.60	8.02	8.56
Cyclohexyl	106	28.13	28.54	8.21	7.61

*Decomposition points are uncorrected.

Preparation of Benzylthiuronium-O-alkyl dithiocarbonates.—

Potassium hydroxide (5 g.) is dissolved in 10 ml. of an alcohol, by warming. The solution is cooled and 10 ml. of carbon disulphide is introduced dropwise. Potassium-O-alkyl dithiocarbonate thus formed (ether may be added to facilitate precipitation of the salt) is collected by suction filtration. The salt is dissolved in 10 ml. of water, and a solution of benzylthiuronium chloride (5 g.) in 10 ml. of water is introduced dropwise with stirring. Benzylthiuronium-O-alkyl dithiocarbonates are precipitated at room temperature in most cases however, chilling is necessary in some cases. The salts are collected by suction filtration and recrystallized from ethanol. Yields are 80-90%. The salts have been observed to undergo slow decomposition during storage.

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